

Accumulation of Martian Dust as a Mechanism of a Motion of Working Systems Through MIRCE Space

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Abstract:

The main objective of this paper is to address the accumulation of Martian dust as a mechanism of the motion of working systems in MIRCE Science. A specific example is related to NASA's InSight Mars Lander that spent four-year working on Mars. It is a planet with the largest dust storms in the Solar System, which can vary from a storm over a small area, to gigantic storms that cover the entire planet. Frequent Martian storms blanketed the solar panels of the lander with dust, blocking much of the sunlight it needs to charge its

batteries. The paper starts with the analyses of the design team's decisions not to have any cleaning devices on the solar panels to reduce the launch weight and finishes with the operational challenges that faced the management team in attempts to clean the solar panels during the last days of its working life. As human ambitions for exploring surrounding space are endless, the lesson learned from the InSight's successful mission on the planet Mars is that it is necessary to establish the balance between a lander launching functionality on the Earth and lander mission functionality in the Solar System. MIRCE Science is a theory developed to predict the motion of a working system through MIRCE Space, caused by any action whatsoever and it is used to determine the actions and resources required for doing expected work in existing location.

Keywords: MIRCE Science, Planet Mars, Martian dust, functionality of InSight lander.

Introduction

The philosophy of MIRCE Science is based on the premise that the purpose of the existence of any working system is to do work (Knezevic, 2004). The work is considered to be done when the expected measurable function is performed through time. To increase the amount of work done it is necessary to reduce the probability of occurrences of negative functionality events. In that aid MIRCE Science focuses on the scientific understanding and description of the physical phenomena and human actions that govern the motion of working systems through MIRCE Space. A full understanding of the mechanisms that generate this motion is

essential for the accurate predictions of the functionality performance of a working system type using the mathematical scheme of MIRCE Science (Knezevic, 2017).

The main objective of this paper is to address the accumulation of Martian dust as a mechanism of the motion of working systems on Mars through MIRCE Space, through experience of NASA's InSight Mars Lander, which spent four-year on Red Planet. Being a planet with the largest dust storms in the Solar System, this can vary from a storm over a small area, to gigantic storms that cover the entire planet. Eventually, storms on Mars generated the amount of dust that blanketed the solar panels of the lander, blocking

much of the sunlight it needs to charge its batteries and thus ended the mission of this, otherwise fully functional system.

Also, author highlighted the conflict within the design team regarding the inclusion of cleaning devices of the solar panels in order to reduce the launch weight versus the exposure to the risk of inability to clean the solar panels that charge its battery, from the extensive accumulation of Marian dust. The former choice caused the final demise of the InSight mission.

MIRCE Science Fundamentals

According to MIRCE Science, at any instant of calendar time, a given working system could be in one of the following two macro states Knezevic (Knezevic, 2017):

- Positive Functionability State (PFS), a generic name for a state in which a working system is able to deliver the expected measurable function(s),
- Negative Functionability State (NFS), a generic name for a state in which a working system is unable to deliver the expected measurable function(s), resulting from any reason whatsoever.

In MIRCE Science, (Knezevic, 2017) work done by a working system is uniquely defined by the trajectory generated by its motion through MIRCE Space, which is a conceptual 3-dimensional space containing an infinite set of possible discrete functionability states that a working system could be found in, at any instant of the calendar time, and corresponding probabilities. That motion is driven by functionability actions, which are classified as:

- Negative Functionability Action (NFA), is a generic name for any natural process or human activity that compels a system to move to a NFS. Typical examples are: thermal ageing, actinic degradation, acid reaction, bird strike, warping, abrasive wear, suncups formation on the blue ice runway, fatigue, pitting, thermal buckling, photo-oxidation, production errors, strong wind, maintenance error, hail damage,

lightening strike, COVID-19, quality problems, tsunami, hard landing, sand storm and so forth.

- Positive Functionability Action (PFA), is a generic name for any natural process or human activity that compels a system to move to a PFS. Typical examples are: servicing, lubrication, visual inspection, repair, replacement, final repair, examination, partial restoration, inspection, storage, modification, transportation, sparing, cannibalisation, refurbishment, health monitoring, restoration, packaging, diagnostics and similar

The time evolution of a working system through MIRCE Space is physically manifested through the occurrences of functionability events, which are classified as:

- Positive Functionability Event (PFE), a generic name for any physically observable occurrence in the calendar time that signifies the transition of a working system from a NFS to a PFS.
- Negative Functionability Event (NFE), a generic name for any physically observable occurrence in the calendar time that signifies the transition of a working system from a PFS to a NFS.

Consequently, the concept of the motion in MIRCE Science is conceptualised as the transition of a working system through functionality states, resulting from any functionability actions whatsoever and the actions required to generate any functionability motion.

To scientifically understand the mechanisms that generate functionability events, positive and negative, analysis of the in-service behaviour of several thousands of components, modules and assemblies of working systems in defence, aerospace, nuclear, transportation, motorsport, communication and other industries have been conducted at MIRCE Academy.

In MIRCE Science all negative functionability actions regarding individual components are categorised as following (Knezevic, 2017):

- Component-internal actions (CIA) that consist of:

- Inherent actions that are introduced into components prior to their introduction into service through the activities associated with the design, manufacturing, handling, transportation, maintenance, storage and similar processes.
- Cumulative continuous actions that are an inevitable part of the components in-service life resulting from natural decay processes such as: corrosion, fatigue, creep, wear and similar.
- Component-external actions (CEA), which are originated by:
 - Environmental phenomena that cause discrete overload, like foreign object damage; birds strike (domestic and wild animals), weather (hail, rain, snow, lightening, solar radiation, etc.,) and so forth.
 - Human activities:
 - Errors that are related to phenomena that cause overload, for example use and abuse by operators, (pilots, driver and other users), maintainers (maintenance induced errors) and logistics support personnel (bogus parts, shelf life, etc.)
 - Rules that are related to organisational policies, legal requirements, national and international, best practices or any other human imposed functionality related actions (scheduled and condition based maintenance tasks).

Corresponding negative functionality events related to the functional system as a whole, are categorised as following:

- System-internal actions (SIA): resulting from processes that are taking place within a system, like a change from passive to active state for certain components and modules, a change in functionality states of some of its

constituent components that impact the functionality of the system.

- System-external actions (SEA): which are generated by:
 - Environmental phenomena related to weather (hail, rain, snow, dust, lightening, volcanic eruptions, wind, fog, solar radiation, etc.) and other causes that impact on the functionality of a working system type.
 - Human activities:
 - Errors, which are related to the phenomena of use and abuse by: operators, maintainers or supply chain personnel.
 - Rules, which are related to organisational policies, legal requirements, national and international, best practices or any other human imposed functionality actions that cause the occurrence of NFEs for the working systems.

This paper is focused on the impact of Martian dust that cause irreversible transition of a NASA InSight's to a negative functionality state, as frequent Martian storms blanketed the solar panels with dust, blocking much of the sunlight it needs to charge its batteries (Witze, 2022). To extend the operational life of the InSight mission, controllers were running its seismometer intermittently to conserve energy until it stopped responding to commands from Earth and slid into oblivion, in December 2022.

InSight Mars lander as a Functional System

It is well accepted that a functional system is a collection of elements put together to performed at least one measurable function. Hence, InSight, short for Interior Exploration using Seismic Investigations, Geodesy and Heat Transport, is a “put together collection of elements, by NASA’s Jet Propulsion Laboratory, a division of Caltech in Pasadena (California), which manages

InSight for the agency's Science Mission Directorate in Washington. InSight is part of NASA's Discovery Program, managed by the agency's Marshall Space Flight Center in Huntsville, Alabama. Lockheed Martin Space in Denver built the InSight lander, including its cruise stage and lander, and supports lander operations for the mission. It is expected that InSight will deliver the following two Mission's science goals:

- Understanding of formation and evolution of terrestrial planets through investigation of the interior structure and processes of Mars. Previous missions have investigated the surface history of the Red Planet by examining features like canyons, volcanoes, rocks and soil. However, signatures of the planet's formation can only be found by sensing and studying its "vital signs" far below the surface. This will be the first thorough investigation since it formed 4.5 billion years ago.
- Determination of tectonic activity of the present level and meteorite impact rate on Mars. The mission will also study the size, thickness,

density and overall structure of the planet's core, mantle and crust. The study will be focused on finding the rate of heat that escapes from the planet's interior, providing information of the evolutionary processes of all of the rocky planets in the inner solar system.

InSight Lander

The Mars lander was built on the proven design of NASA's Mars Phoenix lander, which was an uncrewed space probe that landed on the surface of Mars on 25th May 2008, and operated until 2nd November 2008. Its instruments were used to assess the local habitability and to research the history of water on Mars (Aerospace Technology, 2022)

The lander uses cutting edge instruments, to delve deep beneath the surface and seek the fingerprints of the processes that formed the terrestrial planets. It does so by measuring the planet's "vital signs": its "pulse" (seismology), "temperature" (heat flow), and "reflexes" (precision tracking). Technical specifications of a lander are given in Table 1.

Table 1. Technical specifications for the InSight's Lander

Length	6 m with solar panels deployed ("wingspan")
Width	1.56 m, lander deck diameter
Deck Height	0.83 to 1.08 m
Length of Robotic Arm	1.8 m
Weight	360 kg
Electrical Power	2 solar panels, about 2.2 m each in diameter
Science Instruments	3 seismometers, heat probe, and a radio science experiment
Maximum speed	19,800 km/h

The InSight lander relies on solar power to gather energy. It stores the power in its batteries so it can provide continuous and steady supply of electricity to its instruments.

The solar panels were chosen by the design team in order to make lander as light as possible for launch, they require fewer moving parts and thus increase the reliability. Equipping the lander with brushes or fans to clear off dust was dismissed as, in view of the designers, it would add weight and failure points.

Larger robots that NASA sent to Mars, like the Perseverance and Curiosity rovers use nuclear power, making them more suitable for working in severe environments, but also more dependent on dwindling plutonium-238 decay levels over time. Curiosity is still going strong, nearly nine years after landing on Mars in August 2012. Perseverance, which just landed in February 2022, should have enough power to go for 14 years, according to NASA's predictions.

Robotic Arm

The lander uses 1.8 m long the Instrument Deployment Arm (IDA) which is designed to lift a seismometer and heat flow probe from the deck and place them on the surface.

The robotic arm is attached to the lander deck, includes a grapple for grasping each piece of hardware it lifts. The grapple's five mechanical fingers can close around a handle that resembles a ball on top of a stem. Each of the three items the arm lifts has one of these handles. The three are the Seismic Experiment for Interior Structure, the Heat Flow and Physical Properties Package, and the seismometer's Wind and Thermal Shield.

The IDA has four degrees of freedom, namely, side-to-side and up-and-down at the shoulder, plus bending at the elbow and wrist joints, powered with four electrical motors.

Cameras

The InSight lander contains the following two complementary engineering cameras:

- Instrument Deployment Camera (IDC) that is located on the arm with full colour capability. It has a 45-degree field of view and can provide a panoramic view of the terrain surrounding the landing site. This camera images the workspace in detail to support the selection of the best spots to place down the instruments. Researchers can point the camera in any direction, so it can take images to be combined into a 360-degree panorama of the lander's surroundings.
- Instrument Context Camera (ICC), is mounted just below the deck, on the edge of the lander facing the workspace, which is the area of ground within reach of the arm. The ICC has a "fisheye" field of view of 120 degrees. It provides wide-angle views of the entire workspace at once.

Both cameras have square charge-coupled device (CCD) detector 1,024 by 1,024 pixels.

InSight Mars Lander as a working system

In MIRCE Science a working system is defined as operationally defined functional systems, which means that in-service environment, processes, resources and rules that govern its functionality performance are taken into consideration. Thus, each functional system could be a part of numerous working systems, which means that a functionality performance of a system is inherited from the design and not changeable. However, the functionality performance of a functional system, measured through the work done in a given interval of time and resources consumed, could vary considerably among working systems.

InSight's primary function was to measure 'marsquakes' rippling through the planet, which should reveal how the planet is separated into a core, mantle and crust. Scientists can use that information to deduce how Mars and the Earth evolved differently over the past 4.5 billion years. To fulfil this function all instruments on InSight have to be continuously in PFS and that requires the provision of electrical energy around 5000 Wh, expected to be supplied by two solar panels located on the lander.

Planet Mars

During the formation of the Solar System, as the result of a stochastic process of run-away accretion out of the protoplanetary disk that orbited the Sun, planet Mars was created. It has many distinctive chemical features caused by its position in the Solar System. Elements with comparatively low boiling points such as chlorine, phosphorus and sulphur are much more common on Mars than Earth. These elements were probably removed from areas closer to the Sun by the young star's energetic solar wind.

Due to Mars's greater distance from the Sun, the Martian year is about two Earth years long. Martian surface temperatures vary from lows of about -143°C (at the winter polar caps) to highs of up to 35°C (in equatorial summer). The wide

range in temperatures is due to the thin atmosphere that cannot store much solar heat, the low atmospheric pressure and the low thermal inertia of Martian soil. As Mars is also 1.52 times as far from the Sun as Earth, it receives just 43% of the amount of sunlight.

Mars Atmosphere

All of the Solar System planets have atmospheres, as gravity generated by their large masses is strong enough to keep gaseous particles close to the surface. The larger gas giants are massive enough to keep large amounts of the light gases hydrogen and helium close by, while the smaller planets lose these gases into space. However, the composition of the Earth's atmosphere is different from the other planets, as the various life processes that have transpired on the planet have introduced free molecular oxygen. Mercury is the only solar planet without a true atmosphere as it had been blasted away by the solar wind, although not entirely!

Planetary atmospheres are affected by the varying degrees of energy received from either the Sun or their interiors, leading to the formation of dynamic weather systems such as:

- hurricanes, on Earth,
- planet-wide dust storms, on Mars,
- anticyclone on Jupiter, known as the Great Red Spot,
- holes in the atmosphere on Neptune.

The solar wind interacts directly with the Martian ionosphere, lowering the atmospheric density by stripping away atoms from the outer layer, as Mars lost its magnetosphere around 4 billion years ago. The highest atmospheric density on Mars is equal to the density found 35 km above the Earth's surface. The resulting mean surface pressure is only 0.6% of that of the Earth (101.3 kPa). The scale height of the atmosphere is about 10.8 km, which is higher than Earth's (6 km) because the surface gravity of Mars is only about 38% of Earth's, an effect offset by both the lower temperature and 50%

higher average molecular weight of the atmosphere of Mars.

The atmosphere of Mars consists of about 95% carbon dioxide, 3% nitrogen, 1.6% argon and contains traces of oxygen and water. The atmosphere is quite dusty, containing particulates about 1.5 μm in diameter, which give the Martian sky a tawny colour when seen from the surface (Center for Planetary Sciences, 2022).

Mars also has the largest dust storms in the Solar System. These can vary from a storm over a small area, to gigantic storms that cover the entire planet. They tend to occur when Mars is closest to the Sun, and have been shown to increase the global temperature.

Motion of InSight through MIRCE Functionability Field

On 26th November 2018, NASA reported that the InSight lander had landed successfully on Mars in a region known as Elysium Planitia (near the Martian equator). The meteorological suite (TWINS) and magnetometer were operational. After landing, the dust was allowed to settle for a few hours, during which time the solar array motors were warmed up and then the solar panels were unfurled. The lander then reported its systems' status, acquired some images, and it powered down to sleep mode for its first night on Mars. On its first Martian day (known as a "sol") it set a new solar power record of 4.6 kilowatt-hours generated. This amount was enough to support operations and deploy the sensors. The mission took approximately three months to deploy and commission the geophysical science instruments.

Since landing, the InSight lander has gathered information on more than 1,300 'marsquakes'. Many of the detected quakes came from a geologically active region known as Cerberus Fossae (about 1,500 km away), where underground injections of magma are thought to cause tremors. A tremor is a continuous seismic signal that lasts minutes to days in duration and it is associated with flow of underground magma, oscillations in magma reservoirs, explosions of volcanic gases, and the like. Most

volcanic tremors are represented in a restricted frequency range of 1–9 Hz. These measurements have allowed researchers to calculate, among other things, the long-sought size of Mars's core and the thickness of its crust. Data obtained from five marsquakes shown that Mars's mantle is richer in iron than is Earth's. All of this information on Mars's internal layers will help scientists to understand how the planet formed and evolved over billions of years.

When InSight landed on Mars it was generating roughly 5,000 Wh of power. InSight's panels have outlasted the two-year prime mission they were designed for and are now powering the lander through the two-year extension. Relying on solar panels for power enables such missions to be as light as possible for launch and requires fewer moving parts, as the Spirit and Opportunity Mars rovers showed, when gusts and whirlwinds cleared solar panels over time. However, in the case of InSight, the lander's weather sensors have detected many passing whirlwinds, but none have cleared any dust. As Mars moves in its orbit closer to the Sun, InSight's solar panels should be able to gather more energy, allowing the team to turn the science instruments back on. Depending on the available power, they might begin by turning some on for short periods at key times during the day, as they've been doing to save energy.

Negative Functionability Event of Robotic Arm

The heat flow probe, a German-built robotic instrument nicknamed the Mole, was designed to burrow about 5 m into the Martian ground. Its design was based on soil properties observed on Mars by previous missions.

However, the properties encountered by the Mole were much different due to the unexpected soil properties it encountered. Despite multiple attempts by the team to overcome the challenges, the Mole was unable to reach the desired depth and take its measurements as designed. Lessons learned from these challenges will be applied for the benefit of future Mars missions.

Insight Mars Lander Emergency Hibernation as a Negative Functionability Event

Since the beginning of 2021 InSight has been fighting for its life as the red planet's unpredictable weather threatens to snuff out the robot. Unlike other sites where NASA has sent rovers and landers powerful gusts of wind have not been sweeping Elysium Planitia. These winds, called "cleaning events," are needed to keep the lander in PFS by blowing the red Martian dust off the solar panels of NASA's robots (Witze, 2022). Without them, a thick layer of dust has accumulated on InSight, and it is struggling to absorb sunlight. Consequently, InSight's solar panels were producing just 27 % of their energy capacity in February 2021, when winter was arriving at its resting-place.

Faced with a drastic shortage of electrical power on 14th April 2021 NASA decided to put the lander in "hibernation mode". Thus, all instruments related to its scientific operations were shut down, leaving only those required for its survival active. Thus, the lander should be able to save enough power to keep its systems warm through the frigid Martian nights, when temperatures can drop to -90°C. However, the risk of a potentially fatal power failure is ever present, as if the lander's batteries fail, it might never recover. The problem with the new operational mode is the fact that the lander would become very cold endangering operation of the rather delicate electronics. Still, there is a probability that an odd dust storm in the next four or five months could tip the scales by piling more dirt onto InSight's solar panels.

Saltation as a Positive Functionability Action

InSight's management team has been thinking up ways to try to clear dust from its solar panels for almost a year. For example, they tried pulsing the solar panel deployment motors (last used when InSight opened its solar panels after landing) to shake the dust off but didn't succeed.

More recently, several members of the science team started pursuing the saltation, which consists of trickling sand near, but not directly on top of, the panels. It is expected that this action might strike dust on the panels with sand grains that would hop off the solar panel surface and skip through the air in the wind. The larger grains might then carry off the smaller dust particles in the wind.

On 21st May 2021, at around noon Mars's time, the windiest time of day, the team used the scoop on InSight's robotic arm to trickle sand next to InSight's solar panels. It was easiest for InSight's arm to be positioned over the lander's deck, high enough for the winds to blow sand over the panels. Sure enough, with winds blowing north-west at a maximum of 6 m/s, the trickling of sand coincided with an instantaneous bump in the lander's overall power. Although it worked, the lander has not recovered all the power it needs, but this positive action added some helpful margin to InSight's power reserves (Whitwam, 2022).

Martian Dust accumulation as a Negative Functionability Action

On 29th June 2021 Elizabeth Howell (2021) reported that Martian dust has accumulated on the solar panels of NASA's InSight Mars lander and significantly decreased the lander's power supply. To save power and preserve InSight's essential systems, like heaters in the cold Martian environment, mission managers have already turned off several instruments on the lander. NASA has also tried a new way of encouraging the wind to blow off sand, but with limited success.

When InSight landed near the Martian equator in November 2018, it was generating roughly 5,000 Wh of power. Today that level is less than 700. Thus the dust accumulation on the solar arrays has been about 80% obscuration of the arrays. The declining energy levels are not a huge surprise. InSight is in an extended phase of its mission to understand the origin story of the Martian interior. A team reviewing the potential for InSight to extend its mission last year warned

that the lander's power margins would require new measures to keep going after July 2021. Otherwise, power levels "are likely to reach critically low levels during the proposed "extended mission" that ends in December 2022, compromising potential science return, the panel said at the time.

Sometimes a gust of wind from a dust devil can blow accumulated dirt and dust off a spacecraft, as happened during NASA's long-running Spirit and Opportunity Mars rover missions. In the case of InSight, the lander's weather sensors have detected many passing whirlwinds, but none have cleared any dust,

The Retirement Action of InSight

In accordance to the 6th Axiom of MIRCE Science, the day was approaching when NASA's Mars InSight lander would fall silent, ending its history-making mission to reveal secrets of the Red Planet's interior. NASA initially hoped to get two years of operation out of InSight, a mark that it long since passed. There was nothing wrong with the functionality of lander, but there was a problem with functionability of lander. The problem was the cleanliness of two solar panels for power, as Mars' atmosphere is dusty, and a layer of particulates has accumulated on the panels, preventing the operation of measuring instruments. Although NASA knew this event was coming, there was some hope that at the was some hope that wind could clear the solar panels of dust, as it was happened in the past with the Spirit and Opportunity rovers. However, Mars was then heading into the long winter season, during which sunlight was fainter, lowering the solar panels' performance even more. There If 25 % of the panels were cleared of dust, the lander could continue doing science, but at the current rate of decline, NASA planned to shut off InSight's non-seismic instruments at the end of May 2022 (Jet Propulsion Laboratory, 2022).

However, earlier in the summer of 2022, the lander had so little remaining power that the mission turned off all of InSight's other science instruments in order to keep the seismometer

running. They even turned off the fault protection system that would otherwise automatically shut down the seismometer if the system detects that the lander's power generation is dangerously low. It was down to less than 20% of the original generating capacity, which means that it cannot afford to run the instruments around the clock. After a regional dust storm added to the lander's dust-covered solar panels, the team decided to turn off the seismometer altogether in order to save power. Then when the storm was over, the seismometer was collecting data again, though the mission expects the lander only has enough power for a few more weeks as of the seismometer's array of sensors, only the most sensitive were still operating.

The operational team of 25-30 members, rather small in comparison to other Mars missions, continued to extract the most they can out of the InSight, while beginning taking steps to wind down the mission. Finally, on 19th December 2022 NASA announced that InSight failed to respond to communications from Earth and it is assumed the Mars lander may have reached the Retirement State. NASA's final statement related to an extremely successful InSight's mission on Twitter was "My power's really low, so this may be the last image I can send. Don't worry about me, though: my time here has been both productive and serene. If I can keep talking to my mission team, I will – but I'll be signing off here soon. Thanks for staying with me." (Chan, 2022).

Conclusions

The main objective of this paper was to address Martian dust accumulation as a mechanism of the motion of a NASA's InSight lander through the MIRCE Space, during its four-year mission on the Red Planet. It is a planet with the largest dust storms in the Solar System, which can vary from a storm over a small area, to gigantic storms that cover the entire planet. Frequent Martian storms blanketed the solar panels of the lander with dust, blocking much of the sunlight it needs to charge its batteries. The paper starts with the analyses of the design team's decisions

not to have any cleaning devices of the solar panels in order to reduce the launch weight. The paper finishes with the functionability challenges that faced the management team in attempts to clean the solar panels of the accumulated Martian dust. In accordance to the 6th Axiom of MIRCE Science that states, "Working system ends its in-service life in a Negative Functionability State" the last negative functionability event took place on 19th December 2022 when InSight lander fell silent (Knezevic, 2017). NASA initially hoped to get two years of in-service life out of InSight, a mark that it long since passed. There was nothing wrong with the functionality of lander, but there was a problem with the functionability of lander. The problem was the cleanliness of two solar panels for power, as a dusty atmosphere of Mars generated a layer of particulates that has accumulated on the panels, preventing the operation of measuring instruments.

As human ambitions for exploring the Solar System are endless, the lesson learned from the InSight's extended successful mission on the planet Mars is that the main objective of any lander is to do the expected work. According to MIRCE Science (Knezevic, 2017), the work is done when the expected measurable function is performed through calendar time in existing working environment, which in the surrounding space could be significantly different from the work environment on our own planet. Hence, for the successful missions it is necessary to establish the balance between the design-in functionality of lander on the Earth and lander in-service functionability in the Solar System (Chan, 2022). MIRCE Science is a theory developed to predict the motion of an in-service system through MIRCE Space, and determine the actions and resources required for doing the expected work in a physical space.

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